

Influence of the hybrid process on the vertical bond strength of 3D-printed PEEK implants

S. Pilehvar^{1*}, R. Heidari¹, and H. Mozaffari-Jovein^{1,2}

¹ Institute of Materials Science and Engineering, Furtwangen University Campus Tuttlingen, Germany

² Department of Microsystems Technology, University of Freiburg, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: soheil.pilehvar@hs-furtwangen.de

Abstract: The manufacture and development of polyetheretherketone (PEEK) medical implants is a global focus. One of the most efficient modern manufacturing techniques is Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM). In view of the problems encountered with PEEK products in the vertical direction due to low layer penetration and the crystallisation phenomenon, this research focused on improving product quality by applying hybrid processes and optimising the manufacturing process parameters.

© Copyright 2024

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

I. Introduction

Orthopedic implants are a collective term for a large class of implants used to replace, repair or reinforce human bone. Conventional materials for orthopedic implants, such as stainless steels or titanium alloys, have high mechanical strength, good biocompatibility and fatigue resistance and are widely used for repair and replacement of hard tissue in orthopedics. [1,2,3] One problem with these materials is their elastic behavior. The Young's modulus of these materials is significantly higher than that of human bone, which results in a stress shielding effect. This reduces the mechanical load on the neighboring bone, leading to a reduction in bone density and hence osteoporosis. Polymeric materials with suitable physical and mechanical properties are therefore increasingly favored as an alternative to conventional metallic materials for such applications. These materials can reduce the risk of stress shielding due to their low modulus of elasticity. [4]

I.1. The interlayer penetration

Polyetheretherketone (PEEK), an important member of the polyaryletherketone (PAEK) family, is a polyaromatic, semi-crystalline thermoplastic with ether and ketone linkages that exhibits excellent mechanical properties and good biocompatibility. Although many attempts have been made to improve the mechanical strength of parts produced by additive manufacturing (AM), the expected improvement has not yet been achieved in the field of high-performance polymers such as PEEK. The reason for this could be the nature of the significant non-uniformities that lead to a decrease in mechanical properties perpendicular to the layer plane. This decrease in strength has been observed particularly at the interlayer interface [5]. Below the temperature specified as the melting point, the

molecular chains are immobile and therefore unable to spread across the interlayer interface. This is due to the fact that even in semi-crystalline materials that are only partially crystallised, the chains may be arranged in one or more crystalline structures that severely restrict their movement.

This mobility can only be achieved by reheating and then re-melting. During the extrusion process, the crystals melt completely and solidify on a cooler and more stable base plate, ensuring the geometric stability of the part. This stabilisation during cooling can be achieved by increasing the viscosity of amorphous materials or by crystal formation. These phenomena result in less interlayer penetration and an increase in surface crystals. As a result, the cohesion of the layers in the z-direction is compromised, leading to delamination phenomena in the sample. The quality of the bond depends both on the formation and growth of the bond neck between adjacent filaments and on the molecular diffusion processes responsible for the randomization of the polymer chains throughout the interface. In this work, measures have been defined to overcome this problem and to improve the mechanical properties of parts produced by AM.

Figure 1: Interlayer joints in z-direction (A) normal process, (B) healing process.

II. Material and methods

The PEEK filament (TECAFIL PEEK VX natural - 1.75 mm) is supplied by Ensinger plastics (Germany) with a density of 1.32 g/cm³, a glass transition temperature of 143°C, an average molecular weight of 115,000 g/mol and a melting temperature of 343°C. TECAFIL PEEK VX natural is an unfilled PEEK filament based on Victrex® PEEK 450. To reduce the occurrence of surface crystals and improve film penetration, a new process called "healing" was introduced. To fill the existing knowledge gap, a comprehensive and ground-breaking study was carried out to investigate the healing effect and property changes of extruded filaments under different conditions. The starting filaments were extruded on an Intamsys Funmat HT Enhanced printer. Two local thermal systems modified this printing process and hybridised the printing process. A new approach was developed and applied to improve the quality of the printing process. The analysis of the cured and extruded filaments allowed a better understanding of the influence of the different printing conditions on the quality of the printed products.

These approaches allow a more thorough evaluation of the printing process and provide valuable insights for optimising part properties. Tensile tests were performed on 3D printed PEEK parts with and without room temperature annealing in accordance with relevant standards. Tensile tests were performed in accordance with ISO 527-2 using a ZwickRoell machine with a 50 kN load cell. Dog-bone shaped tensile specimens were loaded in both XY and Z directions at a deformation rate of 5 mm/min for strength and strain measurements and 1 mm/min for modulus measurements.

Figure 2: Tensile curve in the xy-direction.

Figure 3: Tensile curve z-direction.

Table 1: Tensile test results.

	healing process	Normal Process
Yield strength XY directions	94.3 (MPa)	89.2 (MPa)
Yield strength Z directions	14.9 (MPa)	6.77 (MPa)
Young's modulus XY directions	3.34 (GPa)	2.9 (GPa)
Elongation in the XY	18 %	20 %

III. Results and discussion

Figure 1-2 clearly shows that more layers penetrate each other in the z-direction during the healing process compared to the normal process. As shown in Figure 2 and Table 1, the yield strength of the "healing process" specimens outperformed the normal process. The xy direction improved by 5.7% while the z direction increased by 120%. A similar increase (15%) was observed in Young's modulus, while the percentage of strain in the xy direction decreased from 20% to 18%.

IV. Conclusions

In this work, the healing process and the normal process were used to print PEEK samples in two different orientations, longitudinal and transverse. By using this innovative process, a more uniform crystal distribution and coherence enhancing diffusion was achieved and the overall quality of our printed samples was improved.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support from the German Federal Ministry for Education and Research BMBF, and connected health in medical mountains project (CoHMed) for this research.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Research funding: The author state no funding involved. Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Informed consent: Informed consent has been obtained from all individuals included in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fan JP, Tsui CP, Tang CY, Chow CL. *Influence of interphase layer on the overall elasto-plastic behaviors of HA/PEEK biocomposite. Biomaterials.* 2004;25:5363–73.
- [2] Scolozzi, P.; Martinez, A.; Jaques, B. *Complex orbito-fronto-temporal reconstruction using computer-designed PEEK implant. J. Craniofac. Surg.* 2007, 18, 224–228.
- [3] Alasserri, N.; Alasraj, A. *Patient-specific implants for maxillofacial defects: Challenges and solutions. Maxillofac. Plast. Reconstr. Surg.* 2020, 42, 15.
- [4] B. Chen, J. Wang, F. Yan, *Comparative investigation on the tribological behaviors of CF/PEEK composites under sea water lubrication. Tribol.Int.* 52(2012)170–177.
- [5] Bellini A and Güçeri S, *Rapid Prototyping J* 9:252–264 (2003).
- [6] Androsch R, Schick C and di Lorenzo ML, *Kinetics of Nucleation and Growth of Crystals of Poly(l-lactic acid). In: Di Lorenzo M., and Androsch R. (eds) Synthesis, Structure and Properties of Poly(lactic acid). Adv Polym Sci, vol 279:235–272. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/12_2016_13.*